

Human Resource Management

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Abstract

The Human Resources are the important asset of an organization. The success or failure of an organization is largely depends on calibre of the people therein. Without positive and creative contribution from the people, organizations cannot progress and prosper. In order to achieve the goals or activities of an organization, they need to keep the present as well as the future the feature recruitments of the organization. A RECRUITMENT is defined as, "a process to discover thee sources of manpower to meet the recruitments of the staffing schedule and to employ effective measures for attracting that manpower in adequate numbers to facilitate effective selection of an efficient workforce". I am doing my Business Research Project on the topic of "RECRUITMENT SYSTEM AND PROCESS IN ORGANAIZATION" to figure out how effectively organization finding its employee.

Introduction

Recruitment is a process of finding and attracting the potential resources for filling up the vacant positions in an organization. It sources the candidates with the abilities and attitude, which are required for achieving the objectives of an organization. To increase the efficiency of hiring, it is recommended that the HR team of an organization follow the four best practices. These four practices ensure successful recruitment without any interruptions. In addition, these practices also ensure consistency and compliance in the recruitment process.

- Recruitment Planning
- Strategy Development
- Short Listing
- Evaluation

Recruitment Planning

It is the first step of the recruitment process, where the vacant positions are analysed and described. It includes job specifications and its nature, experience, qualifications and skills required for the job, etc. The candidates profile should match the organization objective to take responsibilities of the organization. Training to new employee's explanation to the working information. Development of company strategies.

To seek out non-conventional development grounds of talent,

- Identifying Vacancy
- Job Analysis
- Job Description

- Job Specification
- Job Evaluation

Identifying Vacancy

This process begins with receiving the requisition for recruitments from different department of the organization to the HR Department, which contains Number of positions

- Duties and responsibilities to be performed
- Qualification and experience required
- Permanent or Temporary
- Full time or Part time
- Development of company strategies

Job Analysis

Job analysis is a process of identifying, analysing, and determining the duties, responsibilities, skills, abilities, and work environment of a specific job, job autonomy. It helps to understand the importance of task.

Benefits or uses of job analysis

- Employment
- Training and development programmes
- Promotion and transfer
- Job rotation

Job Description

A job description is a basic HR management tool that can help to increase individual and organizational effectiveness. For each employee, a good job description helps to understand:

- Their duties and responsibilities
- Reduce employees burden
- Future development of work standards
- Health Hazards
- Summary of Job
- Training and development facilities

Job Specification

The First step is to list all jobs in the organization and its locations. In addition, it mainly focus on whom they going to recruit.

It contains information about,

- Qualification
- Physical specifications and mental specifications
- Training and development
- Skills
- Behavioural
- Planning of career

Job Evaluation

Job evaluation is a comparative process of analysing, assessing, and determining the relative value of a job in an organization. The main objective of job evaluation is to analyse and determine which job commands how much pay. There are several methods such as,

- Job Grading
- Job Classifications
- Job Ranking Etc.,

Job evaluation forms the basis for salary and wage negotiations.

Recruitment Strategy

A recruiting strategy is formal plan of action involving an organization's attempts to successfully identify, recruit, and hire high-quality candidates for filling its open positions. Recruiting agencies that the organization enlists in its attempts to hire.

- Finding clients
- Getting job orders
- Office maintenance
- Recruiting candidates
- House-keeping
- Plant maintenance

Short Listing

After the completion of sourcing job candidates, next step is to filter the potential candidates. It is a key part in recruitment process. Three steps of screening process,

- Review resumes and cover letters
- Conduct a video or phone interview
- Identify top candidates

Evaluation

This is the last stage of the recruitment process. Recruitment is the costly process hence it is important to measure the effectiveness of the process.

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